

PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN THE MEDICAL FIELD OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK CULTURES

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ANNOTATION This article discusses English and Uzbek phraseological units, as well as proverbs in both languages in the functioning of medical speech. The analysis of the article expresses the evolutionary essence of medical terminology using human organs which expresses feelings, emotions and general characteristics of human activity.

KEY WORDS: phraseological units, proverbs, medical terminology, language culture, human speech.

Linguistic typology is a subfield of linguistics that studies and classifies languages according to their structural features. The main target of the article is to identify and analyze the differences of variety of the world's languages.

Some insight into how human languages changed over time may be provided by Maslova's (2000) statistical analysis of language change as shift of language types in a language population. Maslova's paired sampling method combines comparative and typological data and is based on probabilistic modeling of typological evolution of the totality of human languages as a population, that is, the evolution of the world's linguistic diversity. Still, no model of the development of human languages as a communicative system immediately follows from this approach.

The aim of this article is to identify the lingua cultural expressions between Uzbek and English medico-cultural speech according to the phraseological units and proverbs. Some of English and

Uzbek phraseological units have the same meanings in both cultures but a different body-part lexical component:

The way to a man's heart is through his stomach - Эркакнинг кўнглига ошқозон оркали йўл топиш мумкин.

In this sentence the meaning of the expression is the similar but it is given the finding of way to male's heart is to fulfill his stomach with food. Therefore, to be very close with man and approach attractiveness of opposite gender in relationship. The following phraseological units have the same logical meaning in Uzbek and English languages but with a non-body part:

To have a golden heart - бағри кенг инсон, кўнгли очик

To steal somebody's heart - кимнидир юрагини ўғирламок

Somebody's heart is in their boots - кимнидир кўнгли гап кўтармайди

The examples abovementioned illustrate that given words do not have relationship between human organism but connects with feelings, emotions and condition of human being. "Golden heart" express about the character of person from the positive point of view. "Steal heart" emotions of the verbs love and like, how someone has sympathy to the opposite gender that expressed by phraseological units. Some proverbs in English and Uzbek express the same meanings in the both languages culture that define to be further from appointment place and not being close to speaker.

Far from eyes far from heart - кўздан йироқ кўнгилдан йироқ,

In the following proverb the author describe the phraseological units that express negative emotions of human life. The meaning of the proverb determines how the person live hardly, suffer from poverty and difficulties of living condition.

To live from hand to mouth – жуда қийин шароитда яшамок

The other example proverb in English is:

If you cannot bite, never show your teeth – агар тишлолмасанг, тишингни кўрсатма
that illustrate the behavior of person being to be ready for doing some actions before making progress.

So, medical terminology consists of many parts and forming notions. Any language system, including the English language offers a huge material for deeper investigation of this necessary and interesting concepts, its functioning and development.

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